

Original Research Article

Scholastic Planning and Strategy of Secondary School Teachers Regarding Capability Based Teacher Education: A Comparative Study

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Abstract

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The present research was conducted on the topic “Scholastic planning and strategy of Secondary School teachers (Conventional, online and NTS) regarding capability based teacher education: A Comparative study”. This was descriptive study in nature. Multistage and stratified random sampling techniques were used. A self-developed questionnaire was used in this study based on a five point Likert scale. The inferential statistic ANOVA, and descriptive statistic coefficient of variation, standard deviation and mean were used for data analysis. The Instructional planning and strategy competency score of NTS teachers was consistent as compared to conventional and online SSTs regarding CBTE. So, it was concluded that the national testing service mode of selection was better than the other two. It was recommended that refresher courses might be conducted for conventional and online teachers to improve the Scholastic planning and strategy capability.

Keywords: Analysis of variance, Capability based teachers’ education, Conventional teachers, National testing service teachers, Online teachers

INTRODUCTION

The recruitment of teachers in Pakistan has not been appealing as bias, political interference, ghost teachers and nontransparent practices to control the entire Scholastic system (Alam, 2015). In 2006, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa AWAMI National Party (ANP) decided to recruit the secondary school teachers through its Schools and Literacy Department from all interested contestants acquiring BA/BSc degree along with Bed/B.S Ed for the periods of six-month only. These are called online secondary school teachers (SSTs). Again in 2014, Pakistan TEHREEK E INSAF (PTI) Government in KP tried to recruit SSTs and lower categories of teachers through national testing service (NTS). These are called NTS teachers (Iqbal, 2013).

Teachers perform a vital role in the teaching learning environment. Teacher performs many activities in the classroom during teaching. He effectively communicates the important concepts, motivates, and disciplines the students and keeps individual differences of the students in mind. Although all the mentioned points are very crucial but Scholastic planning of the teachers connect all these points in one chain. This Scholastic planning makes the teachers’ lesson smooth, effective and enthusiastic. It reduces the teacher labour, time and resources (Atta, 2013).

Scholastic planning is the most important responsibility of the teachers. Teacher’s every day job contains their pupils’ studies, fulfil the requirements of the curriculum,

society demands and expectations. Teachers must keep the needs and interests of the students as well as contribute as much as possible to making the teaching in tough and rough situations. To overcome all these types of circumstances, teachers need Scholastic planning and essential practical and theoretical knowledge (Yinger and Hendricks-Lee, 2000).

In the present study researcher wants to compare which one mode of selected teachers has the excellent Scholastic planning and strategy capability. This capability is actually the skill of a tutor to imagine and predict into the future of what, why and how the teaching learning process takes place. Scholastic planning offers rational sequencing, and stepping the lesson. It also saves energy, time, provides a variety of Scholastic objectives, chances to provide higher level questioning to the students, guide teachers, correlate different Scholastic events and prepare students for the everyday activities. Teacher attitudes, belief, orientation and teacher's social background are the component of Scholastic planning. Besides this students age, background, knowledge, motivational level of students, types of content, textbook and other materials influencing the planning process (Zulueta, 2006).

Research Objectives

The objectives of the present research work were following

1. To find out the Scholastic planning and strategy capability of different modes of selected secondary school teachers regarding capability based teacher education.
2. To compare Scholastic planning and strategy capability of different modes of selected secondary school teachers regarding capability based teacher education.

Hypotheses of the Study

Following was hypothesis of the study:

1. There is no substantial difference among the Scholastic planning and strategy capability score of different modes of selected secondary school teachers regarding capability based teacher education.

Significance of the Study

The given research work obviously showed as one of the main chains of progress in the field of teachers training and recruitment. The present research absolutely be turning point in the area of teacher's education and training. Ideal teachers of the nation are pictures of the astonishing and gifted eventual fate of the youths. The

research may help the policy makers and educators and selectors to choose some suitable selection principles for every level of educators.

This study may also guide the school heads, scholastic administrators and Scholastic policy makers to understand the Scholastic Planning and strategy of each category of teachers. Policy makers might better judge that which one teachers having better skill in the Scholastic Planning and strategy come in comparative perspective. The study in hand may also provide guidelines for further researchers and recruitment personnel that one criteria of teacher's selection is the best one.

Research limitation

Standardized Instrument was not available for this study to find the scholastic planning and strategy capability. Researchers developed a self-made questionnaire to find the scores of Scholastic planning and strategy capability for different modes of selected secondary school teachers regarding capability based teachers' education (CBTE).

Research delimitations

1. The research work was restricted to merely public secondary and higher secondary schools of Dera Ismail Khan only.
2. Those Secondary School teachers who were selected through conventional, online and NTS way were taken for the study.

Literature Review

Capability is the skill and knowledge that empower the teacher to be effective. Teachers should have a wide variety of competencies to handle the complex environment of a class. Teaching profession is actually the integration of professional judgement and proficient use of teaching competencies. Many studies on education practices indicate, mainly four classes of competencies produce the highest scores, in which Scholastic planning and strategy capability, classroom management capability, formative assessment and personal competencies of the teachers. So Scholastic planning and strategy capability is very important for a successful teacher.

The instruction word came from the word instruct means to 'to teach'. The transfer of learning from one person to another is generally called instruction. When someone acts or directs, you are actually receiving instruction. Instructions are a set of information which tell us how to teach, why to teach and what to teach. The

more use of technology makes our lives easier so; we require more instructions to use this technology better (The Challenge, 2015).

Planning is the process before going to start the actual situation. The quality teaching is generally related with quality planning. A worthy educator must have comprehensive awareness about national goals, aims and objectives in effective planning. The nature of the planning process is critical and cyclical. Teachers design the classroom activities, select some strategies, implement these strategies in the classroom situation, assess the learner achievement and at last re-plan to cover some shortcoming and further improvement in the planning (Naz, 2016).

Scholastic planning consists of developing specific and general objectives, learning activities, clear cut Scholastic plans and assessment system to know whether the predetermined objectives have been attained or not (Niksolehin, 2009). When teachers understand their objectives then they can utilize time, money and resources effectively, then students are cleared about their learning objectives and focus their attention on learning activities. In this way they can get a clear direction towards their destination. So students and teachers attain benefits from the Scholastic planning.

According to the National professional standard for teachers' education (2009, p.13), instructors practice appropriate resources and strategies to act upon guidelines according to the needs and demands of the students. Teachers commonly assist in students learning, busy in students' progress, and use audio visual aids according to students' requirements. Teachers play various roles like instructors, observer, listener, facilitator and counselor in the classroom. Teachers use various models, concepts and skills to advance the inquiry and questioning skills among the students to promote high order thinking. Teachers also encourage creativity, curiosity, problem solving and critical thinking among the students. Teachers involve the students in meaningful activities through different techniques. Today's teacher knows how to use numerous technologies to improve the students' learning experience. Teacher changes his techniques with respect to the situations he faces in the teaching learning process.

Scholastic strategy is a method which a teacher uses in the classroom in his teaching to attract, involve students in rising interest, critical thinking, and positive relationships among the peers and improve students' academic achievements. Scholastic strategies cover various concepts of the contents and how to deliver the lessons among various abilities of students (Browne, 2011).

Scholastic strategy is a technique; teachers bring in their routine teaching to assist the learners to become independent and strategic learners. Those strategies are called learning strategies, when students use them independently to complete tasks and meet goals.

Teaching strategies which are effective in any education program comprise, independent study, group discussion, cooperative learning, portfolio development and role play etc. Scholastic strategies can be used to all grade levels and subjects and can cover to all types of students.

Scholastic strategies can motivate and focus the attention of the students. It organizes information for remembering and understanding. It is also used to assess and monitor the learning (Walker, 2002).

Teaching strategies assist the students and teachers in teaching learning development to a large extent in many ways. It includes many activities and techniques that learners practice in their daily routine according to their mental level, mental capabilities and interest. Teaching strategies means different methods used by teachers to assist the learners to learn the relevant course material and be able to achieve the desired goals in upcoming time. Every teaching strategy is used by different methods according to the needs, interest and mental level of the students. Teaching strategy success is judged through assessment of students' learning capabilities by comparing some standard criteria (Armstrong, 2013).

Teachers commonly relate various elements like students' health, parents' economic status and peaceful home environment with students' achievements. But he gives less attention to his effective teaching that puts greater impacts on the students' achievement. Teacher considers three elements namely characteristics of the learners, objectives of the content material and qualities of a teacher. These elements are interlined with each other. Teacher selects various methods and techniques with respect to students' needs', existing resources', time, nature of the content material and ability to implement these strategies in the actual classroom (Luke, 2010).

The objective of the Scholastic strategy is to busy students, inspire, encourage and make them concentrate on the learning. Teachers select and use various teaching strategies with respect to need, mental level of the students and available resources etc. It is essential for instructors to practice a vast variety of strategies, but always keep the interest and mental level and need of the content in his mind. The clever choice and implementation of the strategies makes the teacher lesson more appealing and interesting (Janssen, 2014).

So, it is concluded that Scholastic planning and strategies capability is very helpful and has a positive impact on students' learning outcomes. It has been seen that best types of strategies and classroom situations are positively correlated with each other and it produces the best results among the students.

Research framework of the Study

The following were the theoretical framework of the current research work.

Table 1. Population of high and higher secondary schools (gender wise) in district D.I.K

District D.I.Khan Schools	High Schools	Higher Secondary	Total Schools
Male	71	24	95
Female	45	11	56
Total	116	35	151

Source: District EMIS D.I. Khan 2018-19

Table 2. Male and Female population of secondary school teachers (conventional, online and NTS)

District D.I.Khan Schools	High Schools	Higher Secondary	Total Schools
Male SSTs	101	24	133
Female SSTs	40	12	111
Total	141	36	244

Source: District EMIS D.I. Khan 2018-19

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

Population

All secondary school teachers (SSTs) of district Dera Ismail Khan in high and higher secondary schools were selected for this present study as a population. All these secondary school teachers were initially recruited through different methods of selection like online, conventional and national testing service (NTS) processes. All those higher and high secondary schools were selected where all three types of teachers were performing their job (Table 1,2).

Sample

There were 23-schools randomly selected out of 151 high and high secondary schools located in urban and rural areas of District D.I. Khan. There were 62 secondary schools teachers (38-Male and 24-Female) selected from 23-schools on random bases. Multistage stage random sampling was used in this research. A sample of twenty-three secondary schools in district D.I. Khan randomly selected out of 151- High and higher secondary schools at primary stage. The 62-secondary school teachers (SSTs) were nominated by stratified random sampling from the population.

Tool for the data collection/ Instrument

The scholar self-made Scholastic planning and strategy capability scale was developed for the current study.

Description of the tool/ Instrument

This was a five points Likert scale used to measure Scholastic planning and strategy capability of the secondary school teachers. This scale ranging from 1 to 5, 1 for strongly disagreeing and 5 for strongly agree, was used for this particular study (Y Ganaie and Mudasir, 2014). The items of the questionnaire cover Scholastic planning and strategy capability of the secondary school teachers. The respective tool comprised ten items based on a 5-point Likert scale to judge the Scholastic planning and strategy capability of the secondary school teachers. The tool for the present study was developed on the basis of the Government of Pakistan national professional standard for teacher education in Pakistan.

Administration of Subject Matter Capability Scale

The objective of the instrument was clearly and sincerely

Table 3. Mean difference of scholastic planning and strategies capability of conventional, online and NTS SSTs

Groups/Batch	Sum of Squares	d.f	Mean Square	F _{Tab}	F _{Cal}	P-Value	α
Between Groups/Batches	804.01	2	402.01	3.03	40201.43	0.01	0.05
Within Groups/Batches	3.41	397	0.01				
Total	807.42	399					

Table 4. Tukey's test scores of scholastic planning and strategies capability of conventional online and NTS SSTs

Numerous Comparisons							
Dependent Variable: Mean of Scholastic planning and Strategy							
Tukey's HSD							
(I) Mode of Selection	of	(J) Mode of Selection	Average Difference (I-J)	Standard-Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Minor Bound	Higher Bound
Conventional SSTs		National testing Service SSTs	1.00	.011	.000	.97	1.03
		Online SSTs	3.75	.012	.000	3.72	3.78
National testing Service SSTs		Conventional SSTs	-1.00	.011	.001	-1.03	-.97
		Online SSTs	2.75	.013	.000	2.72	2.78
Online SSTs		Conventional SSTs	-3.75	.012	.000	-3.79	-3.72
		National testing Service SSTs	-2.75	.013	.00	-2.78	-2.72

described before the teachers from whom, the information was gathered. It was also explained before the SSTs that collected information would be kept confidential and used only for research purposes. Every action was considered by scholars to keep broad understanding among all tested secondary school teachers selected through different methods. The data of Scholastic planning and strategy capability about sampled male and female secondary school teachers was collected by different subject specialists of various disciplines (Physics, Chemistry, Biology, Mathematics, English, Urdu, and Islamiyat). This data was collected through researcher self-developed Scholastic planning and strategy capability scale. Scholastic planning and strategy capability was observed of respective secondary school teachers by subject specialists of various disciplines, when the same SSTs were teaching to their students. The expert team gives his judgement about the Scholastic planning and strategy capability about respective SSTs on prescribed rating scale. The same method was adopted for every male and female secondary school teacher which was selected through different modes (Y Ganaie and Mudasir, 2014).

Procedure of the Study

Scholastic planning and strategy capability scale was administered among 23-secondary and higher secondary school teachers. The scores of Scholastic planning and strategy capability score was collected from twenty-four

females and thirty-eight male secondary school teachers. The tool was administered to sample SSTs by subject specialists of various disciplines. The researcher provided relevant instructions to subject experts related to the tool of the study verbally and manually. The subject experts collected the data about scholastic planning and strategy capability by observing and rating the items of prescribed rating tool, when these secondary school teachers were busy in teaching their class on specific venue, date and time (Y Ganaie and Mudasir, 2014).

Statistical Analysis

The data of Scholastic planning and strategy capability about the respective male and female secondary school teachers was collected, ordered and analyzed. The analysis of the data about Scholastic planning strategy capability of Conventional, Online and NTS selected secondary school teachers regarding CBTE was determined. The data was analyzed through SPSS-17 by using mean, standard deviation and analysis of variance (ANOVA) to find the differences among the three respective groups of teachers (Iqbal, 2013). The analysis of variance is a statistical technique used to compare the difference among three or more than three means. There are many situations, where researchers try to compare three or more than three means at a time, then ANOVA is used (Choudary and Kamal, 1998).

Table 3 represents $F_{Cal} = 40201.43 > F_{Tab} = 3.03$ and $p = 0.001 < 0.05$, which indicates there is lot of variation

Table 5. Mean, Standard deviation (S.D) and coefficient of variation (CV) of Scholastic planning and strategies capability scores for various modes of selected SSTs.

Group	N	S.D	Mean	C.V
Online SSTs	80	0.0503	1.15	4.38
National testing Service SSTs	120	0.0819	3.90	2.10
Conventional SSTs	200	0.1098	4.90	2.24

Figure 1. Equate the Instructional planning and strategy Competency

among the scores of instructional planning and strategies capability scores among three sets of SSTs. So, researchers concluded that the null hypothesis H_0 is rejected. So the above table does not display that which one set of SST is dissimilar from the other two sets. So, Tukey's test is used.

In Table 4, the scores of Scholastic planning and strategy capability scores of conventional secondary teachers was different from online and NTS SSTs as ($p = 0.001 < 0.05$). The same condition occurred with online and national testing service teachers in comparison with rest of SSTs.

Table 5 shows the values of measures of dispersion and measure of central tendencies of three groups of SSTs on Scholastic Planning and Strategies Capability. The average Scholastic planning capability scores of online, National testing service and conventional SSTs were 1.15, 3.90 and 4.90 respectively. Similarly, S. D values of these SSTs were 0.0503, 0.0819 and 0.1098 while CV values of these SSTs were 4.38, 2.10 and 2.24 respectively. Since CV value of NTS- Secondary School Teachers was fewer than Conventional and Online SSTs. Therefore, national testing service SSTs score for scholastic planning and strategies capability was consistent as compared to conventional and online SSTs. Figure 1

FINDINGS

The following were the finding of the present study:

1. A comparison of calculated F value and F table value of secondary school teachers selected through different modes as perceived by subject specialist through

Scholastic planning and strategy capability scale was ($F_{\text{Calculated}} = 46939.41$ and $F_{\text{tabulated}} = 3.02$ and also $p\text{-value} = 0.000$ and $\alpha\text{-value} = 0.05$) Table-3

2. Scholastic Planning and Strategies Capability of Conventional SSTs was different from NTS and Online SSTs Similarly National Testing service teachers was different from conventional and online and online gives the different results from conventional and NTS as $P\text{-value} = 0.000$ is less than $\alpha = 0.05$ value in all cases.

3. A comparison of mean, standard deviation and coefficient of variation scores of conventional, online and national testing of secondary school teachers' through Scholastic planning and strategy capability scale were [$M_{\text{(Conventional)}} = 4.90$, $M_{\text{(Online)}} = 3.90$ and $M_{\text{(NTS)}} = 1.15$ $S.D_{\text{(Conventional)}} = 0.1098$, $S.D_{\text{(NTS)}} = 0.0819$ and $S.D_{\text{(Online)}} = 0.0503$] similarly $CV_{\text{(Conventional)}} = 2.24$, $CV_{\text{(NTS)}} = 2.10$ and $CV_{\text{(Online)}} = 4.38$]

CONCLUSION OF THE STUDY

The finding of the study showed there is substantial difference among three modes of selected teachers based on Scholastic planning and strategy capability, when they were busy teaching their students. Tukey's test results also demonstrated that all three modes of selected teachers were different from each other regarding Scholastic planning and strategy capability. Besides this result, graphical representation and values of standard deviation and coefficient of variation (CV) of national testing service teachers was less than conventional and online selected teachers regarding CBTE, shows that scholastic planning and strategy

capability of national testing service teachers was consistent and reliable than the rest of two SSTs.

Implication of the study

The study has tremendous implications in teacher training institutions (TTIs). The Government of Pakistan started an Associate Degree in Education and B.Ed (Hons) program in different TTIs across the country. The study provides a base to the elementary and secondary education department for the recruitment of different categories of teachers. This study also furnished the weakness in the selection criteria of teachers, so policy makers and administrative officers keep the key points, which are mentioned in this study, when they are recruiting the various categories of teachers for different levels.

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